

Research

Influence of Sodium Hypochlorite Corrosion on Stainless Steel K-file and Pro Taper Rotary Nickel-Titanium Instrument

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Abstract: In this work, the corrosion of stainless-steel K-file and pro taper rotary NiTi-file instruments was evaluated and compared about the effects of 5.25% sodium hypochlorite solution. Thirty new Pro Taper NiTi rotary files (D# 20, 25, and 30) and thirty stainless steel K-files (D# 20, 25, and 30) were subjected to a 5-minute immersion in 5.25% NaOCl at 50°C. Every file was put through the corrosion test, which involved recording the open circuit potential (OCP). Corrosion current, corrosion rate, and corrosion potential were all assigned to each file's recording. A potentiated and a standard calomel electrode reference were used to calculate the percentage of open circuit potential (OCP). The frequency of corrosion that may be seen visually was also studied using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The findings indicated that the corrosion rate for stainless steel has the following mean and standard deviation: The CR of stainless steel pipes with diameters of # 20, # 25, and # 30 is 5.48 0.81 mpy, 5.23 0.84 mpy, and 5.81 1.04 mpy, respectively. The CR of #20, #25, and #30 diameters of Niti files, on the other hand, are 2.61 0.36 mpy, 4.53 0.65 mpy, and 5.38 0.65 mpy, respectively. Statistics showed that the findings between the two files were significant. Additionally, both files had pitting and crevice corrosion, as seen by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis. NiTi files demonstrated a lower rate of corrosion than stainless steel files.

Keywords: Corrosion, Stainless steel file, NiTi file

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Introduction

By using chemo-mechanical instruments, root canal therapy seeks to achieve a high level of root canal system disinfection. By allowing sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) to enter up to the apical region of the canal and conduct its bactericidal action,¹ by dissolving the organic materials,² the use of varying diameters of files aids in the development of a continuous and gradually tapered shape for the root canal.

Traditionally, a stainless-steel K file was used to clean and shape the root canal, but this has many drawbacks, including a propensity for corrosion and breakage. Because of this, the endodontic field now has access to rotary instruments with a larger taper and super-elastic and high-strength properties thanks to freshly developed NiTi instruments.³ Additionally, this file achieves good taper with less risk of canal transfer and better preservation of tooth structure than was feasible with manual files.⁴ However, when using NiTi Rotary tools in a clinical setting, several variables could result in an unanticipated fracture.⁵

Numerous researches also looked at the corrosion of root canal files. When these instruments are disinfected with NaOCl,^{6,7} or when the solution is used to instrument and irrigate the pulp chamber and root canal, corrosion may happen.⁸ NaOCl can also selectively remove alloys from the surface, leading to micro pitting because it is corrosive to alloys.^{9,10} These microstructural flaws can cause pockets of stress to build up and cracks to occur, damaging the instrument's structure.¹¹

The concentration of the NaOCl solution affects how quickly NiTi filings corrode as well. It was discovered that after coming into contact with 5.25% NaOCl solution, Ni-Ti instruments can begin to corrode within 1–12 hours, and visible evidence of corrosion can start to appear after 30 minutes of immersion in 5% NaOCl solution. In addition, Oshida et al.¹² discovered a high corrosion rate by heating the 5.25% sodium hypochlorite solution to a temperature of 37°C during the test. While being used in a clinical setting, nickel-titanium rotary instruments can still be separated without showing any symptoms or obvious surface changes. NiTi rotary tools' surfaces may corrode or develop surface imperfections as a result of the irrigation agents used during root canal procedures or the sterilization procedures utilized after root canal procedures. During clinical use, these flaws and distortions might cause instruments to break.^{13,14} The issue becomes serious when the instrument rotates despite having its tip fastened into the root canal or when it is repeatedly subjected to compression and tensile loads at a level that exceeds metal fatigue while rotating in a curved root canal. Because different corrosion evaluation techniques were used in the earlier research, the corrosion pattern is still up for debate. It has been suggested to use a variety of techniques, including atomic force microscopy (AFM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), to investigate the corrosion surface morphology of stainless steel and NiTi instrument surfaces.^{15,16} To compare and analyze the corrosion susceptibility of stainless steel and NiTi endodontic files submerged in NaOCl, open circuit potential (OCP) and scanning microscopic examination were used.

Fig. 1: Representative photographs of scanning electron microscopic observation

Research Methodology

This Experimental study was performed in the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Faculty of Dentistry, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU), Shahbag Dhaka and Bangladesh & PP and PDC BCSIR, Dhaka Bangladesh during the period from September 2020 to August 2021.

Study sample:

Stainless Steel K file (Sybrone Endo, Made in Mexico) and Pro Taper NiTi Rotary instrument (Dentsply Made in Switzerland). The inclusion criteria was use of new stainless steel k-file

Study procedure:

5.25% NaOCl was applied to 30 brand-new Pro Taper NiTi rotary files (D # 20, 25 and 30) and 30 stainless steel K-files (D # 20, 25 and 30) for 5 minutes at 50°C. Every file was put through the corrosion test, which involved recording the open circuit potential (OCP). Each file's strip chart recording was assigned a stability score. Corrosion current, rate, or potential are the three types of corrosion. A GAMRY Instrument reference 3000 was used to determine the percentage of OCP. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) Model: Evo 18 was used to further analyze the frequency of corrosion that

could be seen visually. The maker is Curl Ziess.UK.

Statistical analysis

Data was collected and analyzed by computer based statistical software SPSS version 20. The differences between the percentage of open circuit potential and visually observed corrosion of stainless steel and NiTi files were assessed by Chi-square test and a value of $p < 0.05$ will be considered as statistically significant.

Result:

Following immersion in a NaOCl solution, Table 1 displayed the corrosion current, corrosion potential, and corrosion rate of stainless steel and NiTi files of # 20, 25, and 30. Stainless steel files exhibit higher levels of corrosion current (IC), rate, and potential than NiTi files, and these differences are statistically significant. In both files, scanning electron microscopic examination also revealed crevice/pitting corrosion (Figure 1).

Author Contributions: Mozammal Hossain (Supervisor), Mohammad Ali Asgor Moral and Abdul Gafur (prepare the design of study), Mst. Dil Afroz Bhuiyan (Collect data), Asaduzzaman Rakib (Collect data & create manuscript)

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